

APPLICATION OF MIXTURE LAW TO RHEOCHOR. PART III.

BY M. V. SABNIS, W. V. BHAGWAT AND H. G. SILAWAT

The application of mixture law to rheochor for non-associated liquid in associated solvent has been investigated. The non-associated liquids investigated are benzene, toluene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride in the associated solvent, methyl alcohol. It is observed that the law is applicable in all cases. For chloroform, however, for low concentrations the deviation is somewhat more.

In previous papers (this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 29; 1946, 23, 349; 1948, 25, 165, 575) the application of mixture law to rheochor, when liquid mixtures are considered, has been discussed. According to Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754) the liquid mixtures have been divided into three groups: (i) non-associated solutes in non-associated solvents, (ii) associated liquids in non-associated solvents and (iii) associated liquids in associated solvents. The group (iii) was investigated by us in Parts I and II (*loc. cit.*). In this paper we have extended this work to non-associated liquids in associated solvents (group ii).

To obtain a correct idea of the applicability of the mixture law, it is necessary to study the mixtures over the whole range of molar concentrations *i. e.* from 0 to 1. Similar procedure was followed by Hammick and Andrew (*loc. cit.*) in the case of parachor of liquid mixtures. In case of rheochor, however, it is necessary to investigate the applicability at different temperatures, since the rheochor values change with temperature and rheochor constants are determined from the values as obtained at boiling point. Following tables show our results.

Non-associated Liquids in Associated solvents

x , D , η , M_m , R_m and R_x have the same significance as given in previous papers.

TABLE I
Benzene in methyl alcohol.

Temp. = 30°.

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0000	0.7903	5.60	32.00	50.30	—
0.0572	0.7990	5.62	34.63	53.80	112.0
0.1598	0.8127	5.64	39.38	60.18	111.8
0.2552	0.8221	5.60	43.73	65.98	111.7
0.3449	0.8307	5.63	47.87	72.61	111.5
0.4474	0.8420	5.59	53.36	78.47	111.2
0.7425	0.8551	5.46	66.16	95.68	111.4
0.8277	0.8606	5.40	70.08	100.78	111.3
1.0000	0.8646	5.70	78.00	—	112.0

TABLE I (contd.)

Temp. = 40°.

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0000	0.7823	4.90	32.00	50.01	—
0.0572	0.7903	5.00	34.63	53.59	111.1
0.1598	0.8037	4.91	39.38	59.77	110.3
0.2552	0.8139	5.05	43.73	65.67	110.2
0.3449	0.8219	5.07	47.87	71.08	110.7
0.4474	0.8321	4.78	53.36	77.98	109.9
0.7425	0.8468	4.69	66.16	94.82	110.4
0.8277	0.8534	4.90	70.08	100.20	110.6
1.0000	0.8537	4.90	78.00	—	111.4

Temp. = 50°

0.0000	0.7747	4.16	32.00	49.74	—
0.0572	0.7817	4.15	34.63	52.91	109.6
0.1598	0.7971	4.11	39.38	58.80	109.0
0.2552	0.8070	4.18	43.73	64.54	109.2
0.3449	0.8131	4.05	48.00	70.28	109.3
0.4474	0.8238	4.14	53.36	77.37	109.6
0.7425	0.8385	4.11	66.16	94.04	109.6
0.8277	0.8420	4.13	70.08	99.38	109.8
1.0000	0.8447	4.15	78.00	—	109.2

The mixture law seems to be completely applicable in case of benzene, dissolved in methyl alcohol, the values of R_x as obtained is practically constant although the molar fraction of benzene is changed from 0 to 1 for the same temperature. The value of R_x falls with increase of temperature from 112 to 110. The drop in the value of R_x is gradual and is consistent with the fall in values of R of pure liquid with temperature. The following table with pure liquid will illustrate this.

TABLE II

Temp. ...	60°	80°	100°	140°	180°	240°
R (benzene, b.p. 88°)	110.4	110.4	109.8	109.8	109.2	—

It will be observed that for benzene, temperature has very little effect on R . This is also borne out in the mixtures we have studied at different temperatures. Our value of R_x is comparable with the value of R given in the above table (Friend and Hargreave, *Phil. Mag.*, 1921, *iv*, 84, 943, 644). The value of R_x cannot be compared with the calcula-

ted value, since the value of R for C_6H_6 is determined from the study of R of benzene derivatives omitting benzene as it gives very different value for R (C_6H_6).

TABLE III
Carbon tetrachloride in methyl alcohol.
Temp. = 30°.

x	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x
0.0000	0.7993	4.90	32.00	50.39	—
0.0355	0.8863	5.40	36.33	53.13	129.7
0.1574	1.0640	5.94	51.25	63.10	130.5
0.2723	1.1720	6.65	65.21	71.94	129.8
0.4653	1.2830	7.10	86.50	90.26	129.6
0.6066	1.4380	7.60	106.08	98.28	129.4
0.7506	1.4790	7.66	122.18	108.64	129.5
0.9010	1.5430	7.80	141.98	121.90	129.7
1.0000	1.5740	7.96	154.00	—	129.7

Temp. = 40°.

0.0000	0.7823	4.90	32.00	50.01	—
0.0355	0.8655	5.40	36.33	52.90	129.7
0.1574	1.0440	5.94	51.25	65.52	130.5
0.2723	1.1620	6.65	65.21	71.28	129.8
0.4653	1.2790	7.10	86.50	86.37	129.6
0.6066	1.4169	7.60	106.08	97.71	129.4
0.7506	1.4520	7.66	122.18	108.29	129.5
0.9010	1.5364	7.80	141.98	120.56	129.7
1.0000	1.5650	7.96	154.00	—	129.7

Temp. = 50°.

0.0000	0.7747	4.16	32.00	49.74	—
0.0355	0.8569	5.10	36.33	51.97	126.9
0.1574	1.0320	5.43	51.25	61.32	125.9
0.2723	1.1593	6.12	65.21	70.52	127.4
0.4653	1.1990	6.42	86.50	91.05	126.6
0.6066	1.4010	6.82	106.08	96.16	127.2
0.7506	1.4460	6.98	122.18	107.71	126.9
0.9010	1.5255	7.06	141.98	119.00	127.2
1.0000	1.5360	7.12	154.00	—	127.9

Reals (b.p.) = 122

In case of carbon tetrachloride dissolved in methyl alcohol also, the mixture law holds for all molar concentrations. The values of R_x are higher than the calculated value and fall with increase of temperature and approach the calculated value as the temperature increases. This is, as expected as the value $R_{calc.}$ is at the boiling point of the liquid. The deviation of R_x observed by us at lower temperature from $R_{calc.}$ is much greater in this case than in the case of benzene-methyl alcohol mixture, because the value of R for pure CCl_4 varies appreciably with temperature. Friend and Hargreave's results (*loc. cit.*, p. 644) will illustrate this.

TABLE IV

Temperature	...	60°	100°	186°
R (CCl ₄)	...	126.0	125.1	124.2

TABLE V

Chloroform in methyl alcohol.

Temp. = 30°

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m	R_x .
0.0000	0.7903	5.60	32.00	50.30	—
0.0499	0.8539	5.90	36.35	53.15	106.8
0.1326	1.0740	6.42	43.59	51.14	106.3
0.3228	1.1190	6.53	60.25	68.12	105.5
0.4234	1.1890	6.34	69.03	73.16	104.6
0.5123	1.2370	6.21	76.83	77.62	103.4
0.6081	1.3440	6.08	93.07	86.80	102.6
0.8262	1.3960	6.10	104.28	93.67	102.8
1.0000	1.4590	6.10	119.50	—	102.9

Temp. = 40°.

0.0000	0.7823	4.90	32.00	50.01	—
0.0499	0.8441	5.27	36.35	52.88	105.7
0.1326	1.0610	5.57	43.59	50.89	105.2
0.3228	1.1090	5.66	60.25	67.50	103.9
0.4234	1.1690	5.54	69.03	72.98	104.1
0.5123	1.2290	5.49	76.83	77.29	103.4
0.6081	1.3290	5.45	93.07	86.56	102.3
0.8262	1.3750	5.50	104.28	93.57	102.8
1.0000	1.4440	5.57	119.50	—	102.8

TABLE V (contd.)

Temp. = 50°

x .	D.	$\eta \times 10^3$	Mm.	Rm.	Rz.
0.0000	0.7747	4.16	32.00	49.71	—
0.0499	0.8337	4.39	36.35	52.46	105.0
0.1326	1.1040	4.48	43.59	50.54	104.9
0.3228	1.1083	4.51	60.25	67.14	103.7
0.4234	1.1570	4.68	69.03	72.34	103.6
0.5123	1.2270	4.74	76.83	76.09	102.8
0.6081	1.3130	4.82	93.07	86.26	102.7
0.8262	1.3690	4.96	104.28	93.09	102.3
1.0000	1.4240	4.91	119.50	—	102.3

Reals. (b.p.) = 100.2

TABLE VI

Toluene in methyl alcohol.

Temp. = 30°

x .	D.	$\eta \times 10^3$.	Mm.	Rm.	Rz.
0.0000	0.7903	5.60	32.00	50.30	—
0.0724	0.8044	5.88	36.35	60.26	134.4
0.1636	0.8179	5.88	41.84	63.84	133.0
0.3517	0.8307	5.69	53.15	79.05	133.3
0.5095	0.8392	5.44	62.66	92.26	132.6
0.6126	0.8447	5.39	68.85	100.61	132.4
0.7321	0.8494	5.32	76.04	110.27	132.2
0.8541	0.8551	5.27	83.12	119.50	132.0
1.0000	0.8586	5.38	92.14	—	132.4

Temp. = 40°.

0.0000	0.7823	4.90	32.00	50.01	—
0.0724	0.7938	5.00	36.35	59.84	131.5
0.1636	0.8050	5.03	41.84	63.59	132.4
0.3517	0.8221	4.87	53.15	78.79	131.7
0.5095	0.8303	4.83	62.66	91.94	132.2
0.6126	0.8351	4.80	68.85	100.03	131.6
0.7321	0.8422	4.75	76.04	109.70	131.5
0.8541	0.8437	4.64	83.12	119.50	131.4
1.0000	0.8498	4.81	92.14	—	131.9

TABLE VI (contd.)

Temp. = 50°.

$\%$	$D.$	$\eta \times 10^3.$	$M_m.$	$R_m.$	$R_x.$
0.0000	0.7747	4.16	32.00	49.71	—
0.0724	0.7859	4.33	36.35	59.30	130.2
0.1636	0.7962	4.41	41.84	63.27	129.7
0.3517	0.8127	4.07	53.15	77.82	130.5
0.5095	0.8215	4.20	62.66	91.28	131.2
0.6126	0.8239	4.13	68.85	99.76	131.4
0.7321	0.8283	4.10	76.04	109.45	131.3
0.8541	0.8377	4.08	83.12	118.20	130.3
1.0000	0.8403	4.24	92.14	—	131.4

 $R_{calc.} (b.p.) = 130$

The results obtained for CHCl_3 and CCl_4 in methyl alcohol are similar. The value of R_x falls with temperature as expected. In case of CHCl_3 , however, at lower concentrations the value of R_x deviates rather appreciably, but for higher concentrations the deviation is not appreciable. The high results at lower concentrations or for dilute solutions have been obtained at all the three temperatures, although the variation is much less at higher temperatures. Toluene, however, does not show this discrepancy. Thus, it may be stated that the mixture law is applicable for non-associated liquids in associated solvent, methyl alcohol.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
MADHAV COLLEGE, UJJAIN
AND
HOLKAR COLLEGE, INDORE.

Received August 22, 1949.